

GENDER DISPARITY IN RELATION TO THE TEACHER-EDUCATORS' CREATIVE THINKING: AN ANALYSIS

Prof. Dr. Nivedita

Department of Education, Chaudhary Devi Lal University, Sirsa, Haryana

Email- dr.nivedita@gmail.com

Amit Kumar

Research Scholar, Ph. D. Education, Department of Education, Chaudhary Devi Lal

University, Sirsa, Haryana Email- amittirupati2006@gmail.com

Paper Received On: 20 MAY 2025

Peer Reviewed On: 24 JUNE 2025

Published On: 01 JULY 2025

Abstract

Creativity being an important cognitive aspect to excel thinking outside the box leads manifestation to the innovations. It is essential to identify and nurture the creative potentialities of teacher-educators, so that it may be transformed to classrooms. The present investigation was undertaken to study the creativity of teacher-educators with regards to fluency, flexibility, originality, elaboration and abstractness. A representative sample of 50 teacher-educators from the Teacher Education Institutions (TEIs) of Fatehabad district of Haryana as the field of investigation was drawn using random sampling technique. Creative Test Inventory was used to find out the differences in creativity between males and females of Teacher Education Institutions (TEIs). After tabulating the data in the form of standard scores, the different results were found. Male and Female were found to be significantly different on various attributes of creative thinking i.e. Fluency, Flexibility, Originality, Elaboration and Abstractness in their creative thinking.

Keywords: *Teacher-Educators, Creative Thinking, Fluency, Flexibility, Originality, Elaboration and Abstractness.*

INTRODUCTION

The term “creative” in its tapered sense can be applied to: a *person*, a *process*, or a *product* (an idea, enactment, or physical artifact). According to generalized approach creativity serves several purposes, as it helps to reduce stagnation but also facilitates growth and innovation. Creativity to creative products, a product is creative if it justifies two conditions: to being *new* and must also be *valuable*. Maria Kronfeldner (2009; 2018)

supported with that creative must exhibit *originality* that it does not simple in its meaning “new”; instead, it has to do with the kind of causal process the originator must employ. Originality is an ability to generate a product or idea that is unique or very unusual, unexpected, first of its kind. To be creative both flexibility and persistence are essentially required to face with a complex problem that consists of many different components or constituents, the problem-solver must have to continuously decide focus and efforts to deal with different items simultaneously. Recent studies on creativity tasks (Lu et al., 2017, Smith et al., 2017) supporting the dual Pathway Model of Creativity (Barret et al., 2024, Althuizen and Reichel, 2016, Nijstad et al., 2010) underscore that not only flexibility, but also perseverance, is vital to the creative process. Such cognitive-motivational processes that can be either positively or negatively impacted by external prompts that encourage either exchanging (flexibility) versus dwelling (persistence). These external prompts for more frequent switching might boost the flexibility, and by stimulating novel idea generation via providing new external cues from the environment (Conde I. 2025; George and Wiley, 2019, Smith et al., 2017; Fink et al., 2010). These deliberate and autonomous search or imaginative simulation (Beaty and Silvia, 2012, Troyer et al., 1997; Barsalou, 2003) on a problem or curtailing deeper search or cognitive-attention over resources could, in turn, potentially boost creative ideas.

It is true that originality (or novelty) is a common criterion in most definitions of creativity. However, fluency, originality, and flexibility are primarily considered as aspects of Divergent Thinking (DT) (Orwig et al., 2024; Runco, 2008; Runco & Acar, 2012). Torrance defines creativity or creative thinking using four components, they are as following:-

1. **Fluency-** It refers to the total number of relevant ideas generated. For example, given a prompt to list uses for a spoon, a high-fluency individual would produce numerous valid ideas, indicating a high capacity for idea generation.
2. **Flexibility-** It refers to the variety in the categories of responses. A response set that includes both “eating” and “musical instrument” shows flexibility in thought, as the ideas cover diverse uses and contexts.
3. **Originality-** It refers to the statistical rarity of ideas. For instance, suggesting a spoon be used as a tool to plant small seeds would score higher in originality than common responses.
4. **Elaboration-** It refers to the detail added to ideas. A student might elaborate on using a spoon for painting by explaining how it could create specific textures or patterns.

CREATIVITY OF TEACHER EDUCATORS

This study has been conducted to view the creativity of teacher-educators in relation to their gender and locality of teacher-educators.

Mridula and Jaiswal (2007) found that gender has no effect on creativity and attitude towards science and significant correlation between creativity and attitude towards science. Sharma, A. and Dev, Kapil (2007) found that academic achievement has no impact on creativity. Sharma R. and Tekchand (2009) found that gender and locality has main effect on creativity. Srivastava Y.K and Sivastava PK (2009) found no difference in males and females of higher secondary level on mathematical creativity and different categories of institutions do have significant difference on mathematical creativity and English medium have better mathematical creativity than Hindi medium.

The definition of creativity, like that of general creativity depends upon the way of defining it. Creativity defined as multidimensional attribute that is differently distributed among the people and includes chiefly the factors of fluency, flexibility originality, elaboration and abstractness.

1. **Fluency:** It refers to a rapid flow of ideas and tendencies to change directions and modify information. The greater number of ideas generated on a particular topic or subject matter, the more creative is that person on a specific task. In other words, it is a quantitative representation of the ideas. The fluency may be counted in three ways: ideational fluency, associational fluency and word fluency.
2. **Flexibility:** The skill of being able to discontinue on existing pattern of thoughts and shift it to new pattern is called flexibility, in flexibility, ideas flash in new direction and a person writes as many points as his Imagination can project. It refers to the number of different kinds of ideas a person thinks when faced with problem. It indicates the number of distinct ways an individual can respond a stimulus. Thus it is also the quantitative representation of the idea.
3. **Originality:** It means the uncommon or rare. It indicates uncommonness or newness in the ideas. The more unique, original and infrequent ideas are to be judged more creative, in creativity. this factor count the number of responder judged to be clever, witty and pithy. In other words, it represents the ideas both qualitatively and quantitatively.
4. **Elaboration-** It means the details added to ideas. A student might elaborate on using a spoon for painting by explaining how it could create specific textures or patterns.

5. Abstractness of titles and Resistance to premature closure- This element evaluates a person's ability to think abstractly and remain open to multiple perspectives before forming conclusions.

STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEM

Considering the above arguments, the following problem was chosen for extensive and detailed study- "Gender Disparity in relation to the Teacher-Educators' Creative Thinking: An Analysis".

JUSTIFICATION OF THE STUDY

While gender equity aims the fairness whereas the actual gender disparities occurs in society, which believes to shape the perceptual process and inventiveness. Thus the researcher studied the notion of gender disparity in relation to the teacher-educators' creative thinking.

OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

The researcher conducted the present study with the following objectives:

1. To find out the difference in creativity between rural males and female teacher-educators with regard to fluency, flexibility, originality, elaborations and abstractness.
2. To find out the difference in creativity between urban males and female teacher-educators with regard to fluency, flexibility, originality, elaborations and abstractness.
2. To study the difference in creativity of male and female teacher-educators with regard to fluency, flexibility, originality, elaborations and abstractness.

HYPOTHESES OF THE STUDY

The present study was conducted keeping the following hypotheses in views:

1. There exists no significant difference in creativity among rural males and female teacher-educators with regard to fluency, flexibility, originality, elaborations and abstractness.
- 2 There exists no significant difference in creativity among urban male and female teacher-educators with regard to fluency, flexibility, originality, elaborations and abstractness.
3. There exists no significant difference in creativity among male and female teacher-educators with regard to fluency, flexibility, originality, elaborations and abstractness.

METHOD

The first task of the investigation work is to select appropriate method of research. As per the requirement of the study, survey method was applied. The survey studies are conducted to collect data of the existing phenomena. It deals not only with gathering of data but also involves interpretation, comparison, measurement. understanding and solution of significant educational problems.

POPULATION AND SAMPLE

On the basis of the objectives of the study. the population was decided upon Teacher Education Institutions (TEIs) of Fatehabad district of Haryana. A representative sample of 50 teacher-educators from the Teacher Education Institutions (TEIs) of Fatehabad district of Haryana as the field of investigation was drawn using random sampling technique.

TOOL USED

Self-prepared Creative Test Inventory was used to test the creativity of the sampled population for present investigation.

COLLECTION OF DATA

The Investigator personally contacted the heads in each of the institutions selected for the sample. The purpose and significance of the investigation was explained to them and their permission for data collection was taken. After completing all these formalities, the teacher-educators selected for the test were informed about the tool to be administered.

STATISTICAL TECHNIQUES USED

The following statistical techniques were used in analyzing and interpretation of the data.

1. The measure of central tendency (Arithmetic Mean) and the measure of dispersion (S.D.)
- 2 't-test' was used to find the significance of the difference of the means of different variables.

ANALYSIS AND INTERPRETATION OF DATA

Hypothesis-1.1 There exists no significant difference in creativity among rural male and female teacher-educators with regard to fluency.

't' ratio for the mean score of rural male and female teacher-educators with respect to fluency

Gender	Number	Mean	S.D.	't' Value
Male	25	15.85	3.013	2.09
Female	25	12.89	2.903	

Table – 1

From the results, it is found that the calculated value of 't' ratio (2.09), which is greater than the table value at .05 level. So, t ratio is significant at .05 level. It is concluded that in 95% of chances there exist low significant difference between males and females in relation to their creativity The mean scores of male and female teacher-educators are 15.85 and 12.89 respectively. The mean score of male teacher-educators is higher than the mean score of female teacher-educators. Hence, the hypothesis of no significant difference in creativity of

males and females with regard to fluency stands rejected. Thus gender affects creativity of teacher-educators a little.

Hypothesis-1.2 There exists no significant difference in creativity among rural male and female teacher-educators with regard to flexibility.

't' ratio for the mean score of rural male and female teacher-educators with respect to flexibility

Gender	Number	Mean	S.D.	't' Value
Male	25	17.31	2.840	2.48
Female	25	13.80	3.088	

Table – 2

Results shows that the calculated value of 't' ratio (2.48), which is greater than the table value at .05 level. So, 't' ratio is significant at .05 level. It is concluded that in 95% chances there exist low significant difference between males and females in relation to their flexibility dimension of creativity. The mean scores of male and female teacher-educators are 17.31 and 13.80 respectively. The mean score of male teacher-educators is higher than the mean score of female teacher-educators. Therefore, it can be concluded that gender has role to play in the development of flexibility dimension of creativity. Hence the hypothesis of no significant difference in the flexibility dimension of creativity between males and females stands rejected.

Hypothesis-1.3 There exists no significant difference in creativity among rural male and female teacher-educators with regard to originality.

't' ratio for the mean score of rural male and female teacher-educators with respect to originality

Gender	Number	Mean	S.D.	't' Value
Male	25	16.62	2.888	1.70
Female	25	14.21	3.023	

Table – 3

Results depicts that the calculated value of 't' ratio (1.70), which is smaller than the table value at.05 level also. So, it is not significant. The result of t test shows that there exists no significant difference between male and female teacher-educators on originality dimension of creativity. The mean score of male and female teacher-educators are 16.62 and 14.21 respectively. Although the mean score of male teacher-educators is higher than the female teacher-educators, the 't' test reveals that there exists no significant difference. Therefore, it

can be concluded that gender has no role to play in the development of originality dimension of creativity. Hence, the hypothesis of no significant difference in the originality dimension of creativity of male and female teacher-educators is accepted.

Hypothesis-1.4 There exists no significant difference in creativity among rural male and female teacher-educators with regard to elaboration.

't' ratio for the mean score of rural male and female teacher-educators with respect to elaboration

Gender	Number	Mean	S.D.	't' Value
Male	25	15.01	2.711	0.86
Female	25	16.22	2.921	

Table - 4

Results depicts that the calculated value of 't' ratio (0.86), which is smaller than the table value at.05 level also. So, it is not significant. The result of t test shows that there exists no significant difference between male and female teacher-educators on elaboration dimension of creativity. The mean score of male and female teacher-educators are 15.01 and 16.22 respectively. Although the mean score of female teacher-educators is higher than the male teacher-educators, the 't' test reveals that there exists no significant difference. Therefore, it can be concluded that gender has no role to play in the development of elaboration dimension of creativity. Hence, the hypothesis of no significant difference in the elaboration dimension of creativity of male and female teacher-educators is accepted.

Hypothesis-1.5 There exists no significant difference in creativity among rural male and female teacher-educators with regard to abstractness.

't' ratio for the mean score of rural male and female teacher-educators with respect to abstractness

Gender	Number	Mean	S.D.	't' Value
Male	25	13.64	1.997	0.78
Female	25	14.75	2.023	

Results depicts that the calculated value of 't' ratio (0.78), which is smaller than the table value at.05 level also. So, it is not significant. The result of t test shows that there exists no significant difference between male and female teacher-educators on abstractness dimension of creativity. The mean score of male and female teacher-educators are 13.64 and 14.75 respectively. Although the mean score of female teacher-educators is higher than the male teacher-educators, the 't' test reveals that there exists no significant difference. Therefore, it

can be concluded that gender has no role to play in the development of abstractness dimension of creativity. Hence, the hypothesis of no significant difference in the abstractness dimension of creativity of male and female teacher-educators is accepted.

Hypothesis-1.6 There exists no significant difference in creativity among rural male and female teacher-educators.

't' ratio for the mean score of creativity among rural male and female teacher-educators

Gender	Number	Mean	S.D.	't' Value
Male	25	15.69	2.486	0.93
Female	25	14.37	2.525	

Table – 6

Results shows that the calculated value of t ratio (0.93), which is smaller than the table value at .05 level which is not significant at .05 level. It is concluded that in 95% of chances there exist no significant difference between males and females in relation to their total creativity. The mean scores of male and female teacher-educators are 15.69 and 14.37 respectively. The mean score of male teacher-educators is slightly higher than the mean score of female teacher-educators. Therefore, it can be concluded that gender has no role to play in the development of total creativity. Hence, the hypothesis of no significant difference between males and female teacher-educators in total creativity is accepted.

Hypothesis-2.1 There exists no significant difference in creativity among urban male and female teacher-educators with regard to fluency.

't' ratio for the mean score of urban male and female teacher-educators with respect to fluency

Gender	Number	Mean	S.D.	't' Value
Male	25	16.87	2.694	2.85
Female	25	12.83	2.370	

Table – 7

Results shows that the calculated value of 't' ratio (2.85), which is greater than the table value at .05 level which is significant at 05 level. It is concluded that in 95% of chances there exist low significant difference between urban male and female teacher-educators in relation to their fluency dimension of creativity. The mean scores of urban male and female teacher-educators are 16.87 and 12.83 respectively. The mean score of urban teacher-educators is higher than the mean score of rural college teacher-educators. It can be concluded that urban male teacher-educators are more fluent in the field of creativity than female teacher-educators

Hence the hypothesis of no significant difference on the fluency dimension of creativity between urban male and female teacher-educators stands rejected.

Hypothesis-2.2 There exists no significant difference in creativity among urban male and female teacher-educators with regard to flexibility.

't' ratio for the mean score of urban male and female teacher-educators with respect to flexibility

Gender	Number	Mean	S.D.	't' Value
Male	25	13.64	2.517	1.27
Female	25	14.75	2.497	

Table – 8

Results shows that the calculated value of 't' ratio (1.27), which is smaller than the table value at .05 level. The result shows that there exists no significant difference between urban male and female teacher-educators on flexibility dimension of creativity. The mean scores of urban male and female teacher-educators are 13.64 and 14.75 respectively. Although the mean score of urban male teacher-educators is higher than the female teacher-educators, the 't' test reveals that there exists no significant difference. So the difference found is due to sample fluctuation. Therefore, it can be concluded that gender has no role to play in the development of flexibility dimension of creativity. Hence, the hypothesis of no significant difference in the flexibility dimension of creativity between urban male and female teacher-educators is accepted.

Hypothesis-2.3 There exists no significant difference in creativity among urban male and female teacher-educators with regard to originality.

't' ratio for the mean score of urban male and female teacher-educators with respect to originality

Gender	Number	Mean	S.D.	't' Value
Male	25	12.99	2.694	2.07
Female	25	15.92	2.370	

Table - 9

Results shows that the calculated value of 't' ratio (2.07), which is greater than the table value at .05 level which is significant at .05 level. It is concluded that in 95% chances, there exist low significant difference between urban male and female teacher-educators in relation to

their originality dimension of creativity. The mean scores of urban male and female teacher-educators are 12.99 and 15.92 respectively. The mean score of urban female teacher-educators is higher than the mean score of urban male teacher-educators. Therefore, it can be concluded that gender has a vital role to play in the development of originality dimension of creativity among urban teacher-educators. Hence the hypothesis of no significant difference in the originality of dimension of creativity of urban male and female rural teacher-educators stands rejected.

Hypothesis-2.4 There exists no significant difference in creativity among urban male and female teacher-educators with regard to elaboration.

't' ratio for the mean score of urban male and female teacher-educators with respect to elaboration

Gender	Number	Mean	S.D.	't' Value
Male	25	17.80	2.517	1.99
Female	25	14.98	2.497	

Table - 10

Results shows that the calculated value of 't' ratio (1.99), which is smaller than the table value at .05 level. The result shows that there exists no significant difference between urban male and female teacher-educators on elaboration dimension of creativity. The mean scores of urban male and female teacher-educators are 17.8 and 14.98 respectively. Although the mean score of urban male teacher-educators is higher than urban female teacher-educators, the 't' test reveals that there exists no significant difference. Therefore, it can be concluded that type of gender has no role to play in the development of elaboration dimension of creativity among the urban teacher-educators. Hence, the hypothesis of no significant difference in the elaboration dimension of creativity between urban male and female teacher-educators is accepted.

Hypothesis-2.5 There exists no significant difference in creativity among urban male and female teacher-educators with regard to abstractness.

't' ratio for the mean score of urban male and female teacher-educators with respect to abstractness

Gender	Number	Mean	S.D.	't' Value
Male	25	15.90	2.728	2.00
Female	25	13.07	2.645	

Table – 11

Results shows that the calculated value of 't' ratio (2.00), which is smaller than the table value at .05 level. The result shows that there exists no significant difference between urban male

and female teacher-educators on abstractness dimension of creativity. The mean scores of urban male and female teacher-educators are 15.90 and 13.07 respectively. Although the mean score of urban male teacher-educators is higher than the urban female teacher-educators, the 't' test reveals that there exists no significant difference. Therefore, it can be concluded that gender has no role to play in the development of abstractness dimension of creativity among urban teacher-educators. Hence, the hypothesis of no significant difference in the abstractness dimension of creativity between urban male and female teacher-educators is accepted.

Hypothesis-2.6 There exists no significant difference in creativity among urban male and female teacher-educators.

't' ratio for the mean score of creativity among urban male and female teacher-educators

Gender	Number	Mean	S.D.	't' Value
Male	25	16.39	2.416	2.45
Female	25	15.73	2.025	

Table – 12

Results shows that the calculated value of t ratio (2.45), which is greater than the table value at .05 level which is significant at .05 level. It is concluded that in 95% of chances there exist significant difference between males and females in relation to their total creativity. The mean scores of urban male and female teacher-educators are 16.39 and 15.73 respectively. The mean score of male teacher-educators is slightly higher than the mean score of female urban teacher-educators. Therefore, it can be concluded that gender has significant role to play in the development of total creativity among urban teacher-educators. Hence, the hypothesis of no significant difference between males and female teacher-educators in total creativity is rejected.

Hypothesis-3.0 There exists no significant difference in creativity among male and female teacher-educators.

't' ratio for the mean score of creativity among male and female teacher-educators

Gender	Number	Mean	S.D.	't' Value
Male	25	15.88	2.760	1.20
Female	25	14.17	2.600	

Table - 13

Results shows that there exists no significant difference between male and female teacher-educators in total creativity (1.20; $p < 0.05$). The mean scores of male and female teacher-educators are 15.88 and 14.17 respectively. The mean score of male teacher-educators is higher than the mean score of female teacher-educators. Therefore, it can be concluded that locality and gender has no significant role to play in the development of total creativity. Hence the hypothesis of no significant difference between male and female teacher-educators in total creativity is accepted.

EDUCATIONAL IMPLICATIONS

The present study reveals that most of the teacher-educators have considerable levels of creativity. That means these five components of creativity are quite common traits of teacher educators and creativity is not an exceptional human trait biased to a particular gender. Hence, the study implies that, all teacher educators are able to actively engage in creative processes and all of them can develop their creativity, if they are provided with suitable and sufficient enrichment programs. The curriculum designers, teacher educators and teachers have important role to design and implement such creativity enhancement programs or activities based on the above information derived out of the present investigation.

The present study is conducted in a context where there is a crucial debate on prejudiced gender-disparity, while it's locality domain or domain specificity of creativity. All the notions whether based on genders or locality of teacher educators has no polarity. Results of study also were conducted were valid and acceptable. Besides, these studies were conducted on small populations but sample size of the present study also was satisfactory. Development and nourishment of creativity in different subject areas also is an important curricular objective in today's curriculum. Also, development of advanced and comprehensive creativity tests specific to different domains, to different age levels. quantitative and qualitative assessment of creativity by a number of experts in the field are very important to be explored.

CONCLUSION

Creativity means original thinking, new types of associations, divergent thinking and behavior, new solutions of old problems, abstractness and a new approach in different fields of individual's life No doubt society consists of individuals. But there are only few exceptionally talented individuals who contribute most to the growth of the society. They create new horizons and set up new standards in any institution whether it is associated with science and technology, literature, fine-arts, business. Industries and social leadership. No

sooner does society become devoid of nature's gift to talents it would start to stagnate and ultimately perish.

REFERENCES

- Akhter, A., Karim, M., & Islam, K.M.A. (2022). *The Impact of Creativity and Innovativeness on Digital Entrepreneurship: Empirical evidence from Bangladesh*, *Journal of Asian Finance Economics and Business*, 9(3), 77–82. [Accessed 18 March 2025]. Available at: https://www.researchgate.net/publication/358982141_The_Impact_of_Creativity_and_Innovativeness_on_Digital_Entrepreneurship_Empirical_Evidence_from_Bangladesh.
- Althuizen, N., and Wierenga, B. Supporting creative problem solving with a case-based reasoning system. *Journal of Management Information Systems*, 31, 1 (2014), 309–340.
- Amabile, T. (1996) *Creativity in Context*, Boulder, CO: Westview Press.
- Arnheim, R. (2001) "What it Means to be Creative," *British Journal of Aesthetics*, 41 (1), 24–25.
- Barrett R. Anderson, Shah J.H., and Max K. (2024) Homogenization effects of large language models on human creative ideation. In *Proceedings of the 16th Conference on Creativity & Cognition*, Chicago, IL, USA, June 23-26, 2024, pp. 413–425. ACM.
- Barron, F. *Creativity and Psychological Health*. New York: Van Nostrand, 1963. Best, J.W and Khan, J.V (2010) *Research in Education*. PHI Learning Private Limited, New Delhi-110001.
- Bhatia and Bhatia (2001) *A Textbook of Educational Psychology*. Doaba House, Delhi-110006.
- Boden, M. A. (2004), *The Creative Mind: Myths and Mechanisms* (London: Routledge), 2nd edn, revsd, expanded. (1st edn 1990.).
- Boden, M. A. (2014), 'Artificial Intelligence and Creativity: A Contradiction in Terms?', in E. S. Paul and S. B. Kaufman (eds.), *The Philosophy of Creativity: New Essays* (Oxford: Oxford University Press), pp. 224–246.
- Bruner, J. S. *On Knowing-Essays for the Left Hand*. Cambridge, Mass.: Harvard University Press, 1962.
- Conde, I. (2025) *Genesis of the sociology of creativity in art, culture, and literature in Portuguese sociology. Integrates: [1984- 85]Boris Vian and Foam of Days: fiction with invention of youth (1984) & Art and culture in the Frankfurt School: reality, utopia, nostalgia*.
- Cropley, A. J. "Creativity and Intelligence." *Brit. J. Educ. Psychol.*, 36, 1966,259-266.
- George, Tim, and Jennifer Wiley. "Fixation, flexibility, and forgetting during alternate uses tasks." *Psychology of Aesthetics, Creativity, and the Arts* 13.3 (2019): 305.
- Kant, I. (2001) *Critique of the Power of Judgment*, P. Guyer (ed.), P. Guyer and E. Matthews (trans.), Cambridge: Cambridge University Press.
- Kaufmann, G. and M. A. Runco (2009) "Knowledge management and the management of creativity," in T. Richards , M. A. Runco , and S. Moger (eds.) *The Routledge Companion to Creativity*, London: Routledge.
- Kieran, M. (2014) "Creativity, Virtue and the Challenges from Natural Talent, Ill-Being and Immorality," in A. O'Hear (ed.) *Philosophical Aesthetics and the Sciences of Art: Royal Institute of Philosophy Supplement*, vol. 75, Cambridge: Cambridge University Press.
- Kronfeldner, M. E. (2009) "Creativity Naturalized," *The Philosophical Quarterly*, 59, 577–592.
- Nanay, B. (2014) "An Experiential Account of Creativity," In E. S. Paul and S. B. Kaufman (eds.), *Philosophy of Creativity*, New York: Oxford University Press.
- Lin, E., Peng, Z., & Fang, Y. (2024). *Evaluating and enhancing large language models for novelty assessment in scholarly publications*. arXiv preprint arXiv:2409.16605.

- Lubart, T. I., Pacteau, C., Jacquet, A.-Y., & Caroff, X. (2010). *Children's creative potential: An empirical study of measurement issues. Learning and Individual Differences, 20*, 388–392. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.lindif.2010.02.006>.
- Orwig, W., Beaty, R. E., Benedek, M., & Schacter, D. L. (2024). *Creative evaluation: The role of memory in novelty & effectiveness judgements. Creativity Research Journal, 1–9*.
- Runco, M. A., & Acar, S. (2012). *Divergent thinking as an indicator of creative potential. Creativity Research Journal, 24*, 66–75. <https://doi.org/10.1080/10400419.2012.652929>.
- Silvia, Paul & Beaty, Roger. (2014). *Ready, Set, Create: What Instructing People to "Be Creative" Reveals About the Meaning and Mechanisms of Divergent Thinking. Psychology of Aesthetics Creativity and the Arts. 8. 10.1037/a0036549*.
- Srivastava Y.K and Srivastava P.K (2002) *A Study of Mathematics Creativity of Higher Secondary Level Student of Different Categories of School of Bhilai Township, Recent Researches in Education and Psychology. 7(HI), pp. 54-57*.
- Sternberg, R. J. and T. I. Lubart (1999) *"The Concept of Creativity: Prospects and Paradigms," In R. J. Sternberg (ed.), Handbook of Creativity, Clarendon: Oxford University Press, 3–15*.